

Recovering metals and mineral fraction
from steelmaking residues

Deliverable 1.2

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Es konnten keine Einträge für ein Abbildungsverzeichnis gefunden werden.

Abbreviations and acronyms

DMP	Data Management Plan
TC	Technical Committee
WP	Work Package
IPR	Intellectual property rights
DOI	Digital Object Identifier

Abstract

This Data Management Plan (DMP) defines the data management policy to be used within the ReMFra project. Moreover, the DMP lists the most important datasets that are (or will be) gathered, processed, and/or generated. An individual DMP is provided for each dataset using the unified form to simplify the collection of the most relevant dataset information. As many of the datasets are (or will be) derived from test trials, it is reasonable to expect that IPR issues will severely limit the final data openness. Even though, in the long term, the DMP management activities are expected to have a positively effect on the reuse of the research data, due to improved quality and clarity of the datasets. During the project's lifetime, this DMP will be regularly reviewed and updated by the consortium partners, to reflect current project progress.

1 Introduction

This document represents the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the ReMFra project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101058362.

The DMP is a living document, in which information can be made available on a finer level of granularity through updates as the implementation of the project progresses and when significant changes occur. It is envisioned that the DMP will be updated at least twice during the project lifespan, as shown in Table 1. Additional ad hoc updates are also expected, when deemed necessary to include new datasets, reflect changes in the already identified datasets, changes in consortium policies and plans, or other potential external factors. K1-MET is responsible for the preparation of the DMP. When required, the document will be updated with the support of all project partners and the major DMP versions will be confirmed by the TC (Technical Committee).

Table 1: Timetable of the DMP versions

Version	Publication date	Change
1.0	31.05.2023	First version of the DMP
2.0	31.03.2026	Updated DMP (= D1.3)

2 Data Summary

The ReMFra DMP aims to provide a strategy for managing key data generated and collected during the project and optimize access to and re-use of research data. The DMP is intended to be a “living” document that will outline how the ReMFra research data will be handled during and after the project.

Will there be any re-use of existing data and what will it be re-used for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded. It is possible that we reuse existing data from the Plasma Reactor and also data from previous smelting campaigns with the RecoDust pilot plant together with the data gathered from the ReMFra trials.

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use? Data samples will fall on (i) acquired observational data (e.g., survey data, production overview), (ii) experimental data from pilot equipment (e.g., experimental setup), and (iii) data generated from pilot campaigns (e.g., consumption figures, product quality analyses). The datasets will have an individual DMP regarding.

Table 2: Data identification of each dataset generated in the ReMFra project

Data identification	
Data name	
Data type	
DOI	
Date of creation	
Contact person	
Data summary	
Data description, purpose and relation to the project objectives	
Data origin	
Contributors and roles	
Size of data	
Data utility	
Standards and conventions	
Methodologies for collection or generation	
Format of data	
Metadata	
Archiving and preservation	
Location(s)	
Retention period(s)	
Data exploitation and sharing	
Data openly available	
Level of accessibility	
Justification	
License type	
Searchable keywords	

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project? We will get process data from the Plasma Reactor and the RecoDust pilot plant. With the generated data, the process can be evaluated.

What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use? This will be pursued within the duration of the project.

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used? The data is either generated during the trials with the Plasma Reactor or the RecoDust pilot plant.

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project? The data can be useful to any steel producer, plant supplier, and researcher.

3 FAIR data

ReMFra is dedicated to promoting FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable) data.

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Text documents, presentations, video recordings, and tables produced as part of ReMFra will adhere to a clear naming convention based on best practices. All project-related documents will be assigned to a Work Package and will include document information as part of version control. Templates for presentations, deliverables, and milestones were made available for all project participants. Survey data will be stored with clear naming convention based on best practices as well. Processed data from surveys will follow clear rules for names of variables, values, and coding. Data entries in the ReMFra Information Platform will be tagged with keywords, upon which data can be filtered to enhance findability/discoverability. We will aim to have persistent identifiers for as much of the data as possible, via submission of final outputs, such as the Green Paper, to recognized archives providing Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) or via uploading project documents (at least public deliverables) on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>). Internal persistent identifiers, DOIs, as well as versioning of documents, will be used to allow discovery of data in the internal ReMFra Data Storage as well as in the publicly available ReMFra Information Platform.

Will data be identified by a persistent identifier? The data will have a persistent identifier when they are published on Zenodo.

Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. Metadata? Every dataset will have standard Zenodo metadata.

Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use? The keywords will be ReMFra, circular economy, Plasma Reactor, and RecoDust.

Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed? Yes, Zenodo offers metadata in a format that can be harvested and indexed. Zenodo supports widely

adopted metadata standards, such as Dublin Core and DataCite, which facilitate interoperability and indexing of the metadata. These standards ensure that the metadata associated with the datasets can be easily harvested, indexed, and integrated into various data discovery platforms and search engines, enabling broader visibility and accessibility of the data.

3.2 Making data accessible

Repository:

Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository? The data will be deposited in the repository of TENARIS and Zenodo.

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited? With the repository Zenodo, no arrangements are necessary.

Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object? Zenodo ensures that the data is assigned an identifier. Zenodo assigns a Digital Object IDENTIFIER (DOI) to each dataset deposited in its repository, providing a persistent and unique identifier for easy citation and referencing.

Data:

Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement. Generally, all research data underpinning publications should be made available. As mentioned in the Grant Agreement, Deliverables 3.1 and 7.2 have a sensitive dissemination level.

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible. At the moment, no embargo is applied.

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol? Zenodo supports various access protocols, including the widely used HTTP and HTTPS protocols, making the data accessible through standard web browsers.

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project? This will be pursued within the duration of the project.

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained? This will be pursued within the duration of the project.

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)? At the moment, there is no need for a data access committee.

Metadata.

Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data? Zenodo provides free and standardized access to data through protocols such as HTTP and HTTPS. Users can access and download the data deposited in Zenodo using these widely supported and accessible protocols without any cost. Zenodo follows open-access principles, making the data openly available to users worldwide. How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available? The answer to this question will be pursued within the duration of the project.

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)? We will reference any software needed to access or read the data included.

3.3 Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

To maximize the data interoperability, the ReMFra data will be provided in standard formats that could as were be read by free and/or open software applications. That will simplify the data uptake and facilitate re-combinations with different datasets from different origins. Free and/or open software applications CSV, TXT Notepad++ SVG, EPS Inkscape PDF Adobe Reader DC, WPS office DOC, DOCX, XLS, XLSX, ODF, PPT, PPTX OpenOffice, WPS office AVI VLC, opencv-python DAT ibaAnalyzer

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

In case it is unavoidable we will provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies.

Will your data include qualified references¹ to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)? If necessary, data will include qualified references to other data.

3.4 Increase data re-use

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)? We will define readme files with information on methodology and so on.

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? The metadata of deposited publications will be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication or equivalent.

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? After the conclusion of the project, the correct management of project data will be guaranteed by the partners with their resources.

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
Yes.

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes. A quality assurance process will be pursued within the duration of the project, all project partners are responsible and engaged in the data produced within the ReMFra project.

4 Allocation of resources

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)? Costs related to the management of data have been calculated and included in the project budget, as part of the activities of WP1.

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions) Costs related to open access to research data in Horizon Europe are eligible for reimbursement and are calculated in the project calculation.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project? All project partners are responsible for data management, K1-MET GmbH leads the data management.

How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long?) This will be pursued within the duration of the project.

5 Data security

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)? Store data in at least two separate locations to avoid loss of data. (e.g., ReMFra repository and local storage at the data owner's location for backup)

Label files and versions in a systematically structured way to ensure the coherence of the final data.

Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long-term preservation and curation?

Yes, in Zenodo.

6 Ethics

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA). Currently, no additional ethical or legal issues have been identified. This will be updated in case any ethical or legal issues arise during the project lifespan. Raw survey data will be shared only among the consortium partners as defined in the informed consent. Aggregated, summarized, and processed data is expected to be made open and also included within the publicly open project deliverables.

Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data? We don't have this.

7 Other issues

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)? No